

Specific Consumer Differentiation: Kosher and Halal Certification

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(1) Sheep from the farm Las Albaidas, in Córdoba.
(2) Sheep from Association of Breeders of the Lojeña from Poniente Granadino sheep breed in Loja, Granada.

Halal and Kosher certification offers several significant advantages for the marketing of sheep meat in Andalusia, from an economic, sustainability and access to new markets points of view. This is why several Andalusian agroforestry farms dedicated to the production of meat sheep have opted for this differentiation in the sector, such as the Las Albaidas farm in Córdoba and the Association of Breeders of the Lojeña from Poniente Granadino sheep breed in Loja, Granada.

These certifications provide access to a growing market that values products that meet specific quality and ethical standards. The demand for Halal and Kosher meat has increased in Europe, driven by the growth of the Muslim and Jewish population. This provides these Andalusian agroforestry farms with the opportunity to diversify their clientele and increase their sales.

These certifications not only validate the quality of the meat and the way the animals are slaughtered. In addition, the agroforestry management practiced by these farmers, based on the multiple use of the territory, transhumance, the use of woody crop covers and the management of the pasture, highlight their commitment to environmental and social sustainability, qualities that are highly valued by the target public and their representatives. The trust and transparency of these systems has been achieved thanks to campaigns, visits and demonstrations aimed at the Kosher and Halal communities.

Economically, it can open doors to international markets, facilitating the export of sheep meat to countries where such practices are the norm. This would result in more competitive prices and a higher profit margin. In addition, certified products are more widely accepted in supermarkets and gourmet establishments, which seek to offer diversified options to their customers.

Training and capacity building to obtain certifications can lead producers to adopt more environmentally friendly methods, thus contributing to the sustainability of the industry. This commitment is leading to a more ethical approach by the producers involved, aimed at producing higher quality meat that is easily identifiable in the global market.

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